

THE PRINCIPLES OF NAMING ARTONYMS BASED ON NATURE AND HISTORY

Azamatova Odinakhan Obidovna

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute senior teacher of the Uzbek
language and literature department

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Abstract

In this article, the fact that Uzbek nomenclology has become one of the most developed fields since the second half of the last century, as well as a number of fields of this field such as anthroponymy, toponymy, ethnonymy, as well as ideonyms, in particular artonyms, is related to the names of visual arts. The research work being conducted and the naming principles of the names in it are discussed. It is no secret that the issue of appropriate use of names, their convincing interpretation, and etymological analysis is one of the urgent problems of nomenclature today, especially Uzbek nomenclature. Artonyms are a component of ideonyms, and as a scientific direction of onomastics, the inextricable connection of linguistics with dialectology, etymology, terminology, morphemics, word formation, morphology, language history, and the diversity of the principles of naming artonyms are mentioned.

Key words: onomastics, nomenclology, principle, ideonym, scope, macroscope, microscope, artyonym, sema.

The ability to see nature is the first requirement of education with nature in education to perceive the world! It can only be achieved by being in constant contact with nature. In order to perceive oneself as a part of the whole, a person must be in constant contact with this whole, not an episode. Therefore, the harmony of pedagogical effects requires constant communication with nature. Aesthetic perception of nature leads to a more perfect personality and spiritual enrichment. The beauty of nature evokes very delicate and pleasant feelings in a person, lifts his spirit, improves his mood, and increases his desire to live and work. Our older generations also felt the calming power of natural beauty very well. That's why, more often, they went to the banks of rivers and streams, to the beautiful landscapes of nature, and lived as a destination for themselves. It is difficult to imagine the beauty of nature without greenery - trees and plants. Words are insufficient to express and feel this beauty. Instead, artists took on the task of describing and filling in this image by naming it. We all know that language plays an incomparable role in the process of understanding the world. "We can enter thought only through words (no one has invented another way)," writes A. Vejbitskayax [2]. It is possible to enter the inner world of a person only thanks to language: "Language is a window to the spiritual world of a person, to the secrets of his intelligence and thought processes. It is a mental phenomenon and becomes one of the methods of encoding different forms of cognition: emotional (sensations, feelings, ideas) and rational (concepts, judgments, conclusions)[2]. Naturally, language cannot describe "the world as it is": each language has its own characteristic, which initially gives a certain picture of the world to its speakers[2]. Language can be described as "a window to the national attitude and worldview"[3]. Therefore, thought can only be described and understood through language,

because language is the medium that provides the most natural way to the human mind for today's science. "The richer the conceptual field of the national language is, the richer the entire culture of the nation - its literature, folklore, science, visual arts (it is directly related to the language, and therefore to the national conceptual field), because it is the whole of the nation, and especially religion is interconnected with historical experience"[5]. The conceptual domain of language is the core of all culture. Picture names - artonyms are one of the main components that make up cultural integrity. Concepts revealed in artonyms can be connected with basic concepts of folk culture. The name of a work of art, recognized worldwide and included in the treasury of the national culture fund, occupies a strong place in the onomastic archonymic space of the language community. "If a work of art spreads widely and becomes a reality of public consciousness, the "second reality" contained in it becomes an objective, immutable element, like life itself"[5]. The works of the landscape genre in fine art form the love of nature and beauty qualities in a person. Landscape art has a positive effect on a person by reflecting the beauty of the outside world has a unique power. Therefore, artists often show the most delicate, typical states of nature, their aesthetic relationship to nature through their works of art. The names of the works created on the basis of this genre can be considered a universal linguistic and cultural concept, which is also typical for artonyms: "Blue Landscape", "Autumn Morning", "Cloudy Day", "Zulmatdagi Ziya" (Urol Tansikboev), "After the Rain", "Silence". (Ortykhali Kazhakov), "Sunrise" (Vladimir Burmakin). Concepts store not only the general knowledge of the entire language community, but also the specific individual experience accumulated in the language. The associative meanings of concepts are also important for the linguistic consciousness of the person who observes and perceives works of visual art. Artonyms representing the theme of nature serve to better understand the meaning and purpose of the artistic work: "Night on the mountain", "Forish landscape" (Tahirjon Mirjalilov), "Ko'kan landscape", "Khiva landscape" (Ne'mat Koziboev), "Tea house at night", "Sayil", "Garden road", "Spring. The edge of Tashkent" (Oganes Tatesova).

Specialists believe that Orol Tansikboev's landscapes in his works such as "Mother Earth" and "Evening of a Warm Lake", "Tokhiatosh" and "Syrdarya" were a new direction of the nature theme in Uzbek landscape art. It is also clearly depicted in many of the artist's works, especially in "Dawn at Qairakum Hydroelectric Power Plant". In addition, in his free-style pictures with a harmony of colors, he expresses the feelings of image interpretation through nature with special artonyms: "Angren-Ko'kan mountain road", "Karakol in Pamir", "Belesda. Kyrgyzstan", "Oloy Valley", "Okshomda Panj" (Urol Tansikboev).

Ethnoartonyms are also found in the system of artonyms of the Uzbek language, ethnonyms (Greek ethnos-ethnos-seed, tribe, folk-onym-name) can be seen in many works of visual art based on historical, economic, social-political and other factors. In particular, Orol Tansikboev's "Ulugbek Madrasa", "16 th Uprising", Alisher Mirzaev's "The Youth of Husayn Boygaro and Alisher Navoi", Malik Nabiev's "The Uprising Was Suppressed", "Against the Macedonians", "16th Uprising in Jizzakh", Ortiqali Kazakov's " Apples of the 41st year", Lekim Ibrahimov's "Amir Temur's victory over Tokhtamysh Khan", "Amir Temur and world history", "We will never surrender", Niyozali Kholmatov's "History of Prophets. Moses", "Pearl chest", "From the history of prophets. Holiday in Shah Suleiman", "Battle of Centaurs" by Sagdulla Abdullaev, "Tragedy of Begjap" by Joliboy Izentaev, "40s" by Lutfulla Abdullaev, "Katta Fargona Canal" by Muhammadkhan Nuriddinov, "Sayyid Baraka Amir is handing over the flag to Temur" by Tora Suleiman, "Jalaluddin in battle" by Tahirjon Mirjalilov These are works of

visual art such as "Year 37". The Uzbeks, the ancient inhabitants of Central Asia, occupy a special place among the Turkic-speaking peoples as a nation with several thousand years of state history and rich culture. It is known from our history that different peoples lived on the territory of our country and left their political, cultural and ethnic traces on the page of history. The future of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is developing in art, agriculture, culture and scientific innovations in every field, is bright. Representatives of more than a hundred nationalities live in our republic. Uzbeks are the main group among these peoples. Every nation in the world has its own history and past. Everyone is increasingly interested in knowing their ethnic history, generational ancestors, roots. The main stages and important elements of the formation of the nation, the degree of their participation in ethnogenetic processes, historical succession and genetic connections with the ancient inhabitants of the region, the manifestation of specific characteristics in the formation of the Uzbek nation, and other issues are among these[5]. Lekim Ibrahimov's work entitled "Amir Temur's victory over Tokhtamysh Khan" is a visual art work dedicated to Amir Temur's military campaign. It is known that our great grandfather Amir Temur had the main reasons for every military campaign. These reasons are to strengthen the borders of one's country, to protect against external enemies, to clear the caravan routes from various roadblocks, to punish traitors, traitors, deceivers, to disobey those w It is known from historical works that it consisted of obedience, expansion of its political influence. For example, Amir Temur defeated Urus Khan in 1379 and put Tokhtamish Khan on the White Horde throne. But Tokhtamish Khan betrays Amir Temur. After he raided Movarounnahr several times with the intention of looting, Temur also felt the obligation to fight against him, and on April 15, 1395, a huge battle began between Amir Temur and Tokhtamysh Khan. The battle decided not only the fate of Tokhtamysh Khan, but also the fate of the entire Golden Horde. Our famous writer Pirimkul Kadyrov emphasized that everyone should respect the history of their ancestors and said: "A person's life does not fit into one era. Because we have experienced the war and several periods before and after it. If you think about it, everyone's destiny is rooted in the ages before birth. Our Turkish ancestors shamed people who didn't know seven pinks. Uzbeks of ninety-two tribes have not forgotten the clan of their ancestors[5]. People are the creators of all material and spiritual wealth. At the same time, he is the one who preserves these riches and transmits them from generation to generation. For thousands of years, our people have been preserving their national traditions, their spiritual wealth, and their language.

J. Umarbekov's work of visual art created in 1968 is dedicated to "The youth of Husain Boygaro and Alisher Navoi", the image embodies the oriental image of two friends. It is well known that many scientific observations have been made by our Navoi scholars regarding the life path and creative activity of Husayn Boygaro and Alisher Navoi. Ulina Suyima G'anieva: "According to historical and some literary sources, Alisher's father (Giyasiddin Muhammad) Little Bakhshi (see note) with Giyasiddin Mansur, the son of Bahadur Mirza Boykara (Umarshaikh-B.M.) "He was a friend"[5]. According to the information given by scientist Sharafiddinov: "The Alisher family is a descendant of Temur's son Mirza Umarshaikh, the family of Abulqasim Babur and Husayn Boygaro were blood relatives, i.e. blood relatives"[1]. So, two great people were born and lived in Herat, studied at the same school, improved the state of Khurasan together, served each other faithfully and faithfully throughout their lives, and most importantly, they made great contributions to the development of the Turkish language.

Together with the themes defined in the grouping of artonyms based on naming themes, several works of art named "Natryumort" and pictures named based on the theme of nationality: "Tunda teahouse" (Oganes Tatesova), "Chavgon game" (Tora Kuryozov), "Beshik toy" (Zakir Inoghamov), "Sogd wedding" (Kamoliddin Behzod), "Ball game on horseback", "Cock fight" (Khurshid Ziyakhanov), "Hashar" (Babur Vahobjanov), "Son's wedding" (Babur Ismailov), "Capricorn", "Wrestling", "Race", "Yoyandozlik", "Spear Throwing", "Stone Lifting", "Student Girls" (Alisher Alikulov), "Kiz KhonAtlas" (Lekim Ibrohimov), "Harvest Festival" (Kutlug Basharov), "Bukhara dance", "Khorazm dance", "Welcome" (Chingiz Akhmarov) and paintings named with artonyms representing the theme of action or situation: "Caravan" (Urol Tansikboev), "Sari Nur" (Chingiz Akhmarov), "Makr and love", "Imagination", "Two Hearts Trouble", "The Song of Driving", "Read Fuzuli", "You took my life away from the tulips" (Alisher Mirzaev), "For a healthy generation" (Malik Nabiev), "Imagination", "Ishq I'm your prisoner", "May flowers open to your step", "Caravan of happiness" (Ortiqali Kazakov), "Conversation" (Lekim Ibrohimov), "Face", "Gholib" (Aleksandr Tyurin), "Halocat" (Sobirjon Rahmetov), "The gang", "Relative resistance", "Hope", "Loneliness", "Secret gaze" (Hasan Aminov), among which there are also picture names containing deverbatives (visual-verbal nouns are nouns formed from verbs or verb phrases), because such pictures often depict a specific moment of action: "Falling", "Burning" (Hasan Aminov), "Meeting" (Alisher Mirzaev), "Theft of Europe", "Return", "Entering", "Running after the wind" (Furqat Bozorov), such as "Going to work" (Nikolay Karakhan). In general, artionim is an individual name that illuminates the subject, but there are also works of art whose names are distinguished by numbering: "Kortrek 200" (the artist painted the series "Kortrek 200" in 1990 in Kortrek, Belgium), "Afghanistan - 83" (Bahodir Jalolov), "GAZ-51. "Etude" (Rahim Akhmedov) and there are other artonyms that express special meanings that could not be included in the above categories: "When there is no" (Hasan Aminov), "Dream", "A cup full of plenty" (Bakhtiyor Mahkamov), "Before and after"., "Secret of Coral Rock Necklace", "Definition of Life", "Spiritual Path", "From the Beginning", "Circle" (Tatyana Fadeeva), "Conspiracy" (Sarvar Yoldoshev), "Cosmic Echo", "Red Curtain" (Sarvinoz Kasimova), "Cause", "Arosat" (Babur Ismailov), "Mood", "Reflections" (Quadratulla Ajimetov), "Meeting of Times" (Muhammadiyah Tashmurodov), "Shavkatsiz Dunya" (Yigitali Tursunnazarov), "The Mill of Life" (Akmal Nur), "The Life of Things", "Umr Otari" (Dilorom Mamedova), "Crying of the Serpent" (Nemat Koziboev), "Last Light" (Nikolay Karakhan), "Evening Call" (Diler Imomov), "Autumn Laughter" (Obidjon Bakirov) and many other fine art works. In addition to these, among the collected artionyms, you can also see a series of pictures based on a certain theme: "National Music Group" series (Khurshid Ziyakhanov), "Kashmir Song" (Chingiz Ahmarov), "Stone Suite" (Alisher Mirzaev), "Golden Prince", "Alice in Wonderland", "Grandpa and Seven Gnomes", "English Folk Tales" (Basharova Laila), "Landscape -3", "Landscape -1" (Alexander Tyurin) and others.

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